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THE ECONOMIC ROLE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the economic role of renewable energy sources in the development of a green economy in Uzbekistan. The economic and environmental benefits of using renewable energy sources such as solar, wind and hydropower are highlighted. The paper also examines current reforms and future prospects for the development of renewable energy in the country.

Key words: Renewable energy, Uzbekistan–2030 Strategy, solar and wind energy, green energy, resource conservation, energy sources, conventional fuel, BP reports, REN21 reports.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется экономическая роль возобновляемых источников энергии в развитии зеленой экономики Узбекистана. Рассмотрены экономические и экологические преимущества использования солнечной, ветровой и гидроэнергии. Также освещаются проводимые реформы и перспективы развития данной сферы в стране.

Ключевые слова: Возобновляемая энергия, Стратегия «Узбекистан – 2030», солнечная и ветровая энергетика, зелёная энергетика, ресурсосбережение, источники энергии, традиционное топливо, отчёты BP, отчёты REN21.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, countries around the world have been facing increasing challenges such as climate change, environmental problems, and growing demand for energy resources, which has made the transition to a green economy a necessity. A green economy refers to an economic system that, alongside economic development, ensures the rational use of natural resources and the maintenance of ecological balance. In this process, renewable energy sources play a crucial role. In economic literature, renewable energy is defined as energy obtained from natural sources such as the sun, wind, water, ocean waves, biomass, geothermal heat, and tidal movements. In many academic sources, the term “alternative energy” is also used instead of renewable energy. Traditionally, energy produced from processed fossil fuels is considered conventional energy, while energy generated from renewable sources as an alternative to fossil fuels is called “alternative energy.” Renewable energy is regarded as “green energy,” and compared to conventional energy, it has a significantly lower environmental impact [2]. Uzbekistan has also identified the development of a green economy as one of its priority goals and is paying special attention to expanding the use of renewable energy sources. In the country, a number of investment projects aimed at developing solar and wind energy are being implemented. This serves as an important factor in ensuring energy security, increasing economic efficiency, and achieving environmental sustainability.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Karl Burkart defines the green economy as being based on six key sectors: renewable energy, green buildings, sustainable transport, water management, waste management, and land management [3]. This classification clearly identifies the main directions of the green economy and highlights its practical areas of implementation.

Reports prepared by various international and non-governmental organizations show that data on renewable energy may differ significantly. These differences can be explained by variations in the methodologies used for data collection and reporting.

For instance, BP reports provide information only on renewable energy consumption used in electricity generation [4]. This approach does not allow for a full assessment of the application of renewable energy across other sectors.

In contrast, REN21 reports categorize final energy consumption into fossil fuels, nuclear energy, traditional biomass, and modern renewable energy [5]. Modern renewable energy includes electricity generated from wind, solar, biomass, geothermal, and ocean energy sources; hydropower; heat energy produced using biomass, solar, and geothermal sources; as well as biofuels used in transport.

Local studies also widely cover the development of the green economy in Uzbekistan and the use of renewable energy sources. The findings of these studies emphasize that solar and wind energy play an important role in improving the stability of the country's energy system. At the same time, it is noted that this sector contributes to attracting investments, creating new jobs, and stimulating economic growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed scientific methods such as analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, statistical data generalization, and logical reasoning to examine the economic significance of the green economy and renewable energy sources. During the research process, reports from international organizations, scientific literature, normative legal documents, and materials from the "Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan were analyzed. In addition, the economic and environmental advantages of renewable energy sources were assessed using comparative analysis. The collected data were systematized, and their role and importance in the development of the green economy were highlighted. Based on the research findings, relevant conclusions and recommendations were developed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The "Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan places special emphasis on environmental protection, reducing the negative impacts of climate change, and ensuring ecological sustainability [1]. In the section titled "Resource Conservation and Environmental Protection," the strategy outlines measures aimed at reducing air pollution, expanding the "Green Space" project, increasing forested areas, improving the ecological situation in the Aral Sea region, and promoting the use of renewable energy sources.

Renewable energy sources play an important economic role in the implementation of these objectives. In particular, the development of solar and wind power plants helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions and air pollutants. This, in turn, serves as a key factor in achieving the strategic goals of improving air quality and ensuring environmental safety.

Furthermore, tasks related to waste recycling and the production of alternative energy from waste enable the practical implementation of green economy principles. As a result, dependence on traditional fossil fuels in energy production is reduced, while the ecological sustainability of the economy is strengthened.

The measures outlined in the strategy for adapting to climate change and combating desertification and drought are also closely linked to the expansion of renewable energy use. This is because renewable energy technologies contribute to the efficient use of natural resources, the reduction of carbon emissions, and the acceleration of the transition to a green economy. Therefore, renewable energy sources are emerging as a key strategic tool in achieving Uzbekistan's environmental and economic development goals.

Renewable energy sources are considered one of the main components of the green economy. Due to its natural and climatic conditions, Uzbekistan is among the countries with high solar energy potential. The large number of sunny days throughout the year creates favorable conditions for the development of solar power plants.

Unveiling the Multifaceted Benefits of Renewable Energy

Figure 1: The Multifaceted Benefits of Renewable Energy Sources

One of the key economic advantages of using renewable energy sources is the reduction of dependence on conventional fossil fuels in energy production. This, in turn, makes it possible to reduce energy costs and strengthen energy security. In addition, the implementation of renewable energy projects contributes to the creation of new jobs and the increase of employment opportunities for the population.

According to BP data, in 2019, 692.2 million tons of oil equivalent of renewable energy were consumed, accounting for 5.0% of total primary energy consumption. Between 1990 and 2019, renewable energy consumption increased by 18.4 times, while alternative electricity generation increased by 23.2 times [6]. The analysis shows that renewable energy sources are not only environmentally beneficial but also economically efficient, making them an important factor in the development of the green economy in Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Renewable energy sources play a significant economic role in the development of the green economy in Uzbekistan. They help reduce the amount of harmful gases released into the atmosphere, thereby improving environmental conditions and expanding opportunities to protect public health. Moreover, the introduction of modern technologies creates a foundation for the development of an innovative economy.

Renewable energy contributes to strengthening energy security, reducing energy costs, attracting investments, and creating new jobs. It also plays an important role in mitigating environmental problems and ensuring sustainable development. In the future, it is advisable to further expand the use of renewable energy sources, attract more private and foreign investment into this sector, and encourage the implementation of energy-efficient technologies. In addition, increasing public awareness and knowledge about the green economy and environmental culture will further enhance the effectiveness of reforms in this direction.

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2. “What is Economy? Here’s a Simple Explanation.” Sociology Group: Sociology and Other Social Sciences Blog.
3. BP (formerly British Petroleum until 2001), a multinational oil and gas company.
4. The analytical center established based on the results of the International Conference on Renewable Energy held in Bonn in 2004, supporting renewable energy policy development.
5. BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2020 data.

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